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ASSESSMENT OF THE BACTERIOLOGICAL AND MYCOLOGICAL QUALITY OF MILK PRODUCED FROM TIGER NUT

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ABSTRACT

Nigerians are now concerned with production of beverages from abundant indigenous crops which improve diet and micronutrients intake to humans. Since microbial contamination into foods is unavoidable, most foods with high-level of moisture and nutrients are prone to spoilage and thus the idea of using clove and ginger as preservatives in this study. This study was aimed at determining the bacteriological and mycological quality of milk produced from tiger nut. Processing of milk from tiger nut was done according to standard methods and stored at room temperature, while organoleptic properties (aroma, colour, taste, sweetness, and texture) of the milk were assessed using 9-hedonic scale of rating by (10) panelists every day for 3 days. The samples were made into (3) treatments (B, C, D), each with different preservatives (clove, ginger and a combination of both) and each treatment had (3) replicates, each with different concentrations of the preservatives (3, 5 and 7g/L), while sample A as the control. The results showed a decrease in bacterial population every time the pH value decreased, making the product sour (more acidic). Treatment B with the concentration of 7g of clove had the highest mean pH (4.9), while treatment C with the concentration of 7g of ginger had the lowest mean pH (3.5). However, highest mean bacterial load was observed in treatment B with concentration of 3g of clove (52×10^7 cfu/ml), while treatment D with concentration of 7g of clove and ginger had the lowest (28×10^7 cfu/ml). The bacterial isolates include; *Staphylococcus* from clove powder, *Staphylococcus* and *Bacillus* spp. from ginger powder, while *Proteus*, *Pseudomonas*, *Micrococcus*, *Staphylococcus*, *Aspergillus*, *Alternaria*, *Penicillium* and *Yeasts* spp. were identified from the produced milk product. This research achieved an improvement in sensory quality of the milk with stability of over 48h of storage at ambient temperature.

Keywords: Tiger Nut; Milk; Microorganism; Contamination

INTRODUCTION

Cyperus esculentus are tuber crops which complete their life cycle in more than two (2) years. The plant grows from a seed cote forming a firm projected root fibre in the ground which later develops into small edible tubers. The shoot of the tubers are leaves resembling that in grasses while the tubers are only a few inches away from the surface of the soil. After harvesting, the tubers are similar in size with that of the peanuts, which improves economy and provides nutrients when consumed. However, the yellow tubers can be big or small in size [1]. Although, studies have shown that different species of tiger nuts exist, [2] reported the brown and yellow are found in Nigeria while the black is found in Ghana. Besides the fact that *C. esculentus* can be raw as fresh, dried or not fully dried, or prepared as snacks because of its sweet and nutty taste [3], it can be usefully converted into tiger nut milk juice locally called "Kunun Aya" in Hausa, flour and oil [4].

Moreover, the tubers can be made into biscuits, candies, chocolates, and cookies all in an attempt to boost the economy and checkmate food security [5]. Research by [2] has ruled out the consequences of varieties of tiger nut in relation to its planting site, period and methods upon the minerals, anti-nutrients and Amino acids components in it. Dates are a significant crop in the Arab world and are regarded as an ideal food because they are packed with minerals, vitamins, dietary fiber, and strong antioxidant and phenolic compounds that have anti-mutagenic properties [6]. Many date varieties have glycemic indexes (GIs) that fall between low and medium. The GI varied from 48 to 58 for the Omani date varieties; Khalas, Khasab, and Fard [7]. In contrast, the GI values of the dates from the United Arab Emirates (Fard, Lulu, Bomaan, Dabbas, and Khalas) varied from 46 to 55. Khalas dates have a low GI value when consumed on its own or in combination with plain yogurt [8].

A combination of sugar and date fruit was used to create a low-calorie, low-glycemic-index (GI) soft ice cream that did not compromise its physicochemical or sensory qualities. The date ice cream's GI value (72.5 to 79.0) and caloric value (143.0 to 113.5 kcal) were considerably reduced when date fruit was used in place of sugar. When preparing bread, replacing sugar with date palm pulp meal enhanced the food's nutritious content and demonstrated no detrimental impact on the acceptability of it all overall [9]. However, clove, *Syzygium aromaticum* is noted for its aromatic odour and spicy flavor, which can be linked to eugenol, the predominant volatile ingredient [10]. Clove flower buds are highly prized spices and a key component of Mediterranean cuisine. Antibacterial, antifungal, antiprotozoal, anti-inflammatory, anesthetic, and insecticidal properties of *S. aromaticum* have been reported. A number of plant phenolic compounds categorized as generally regarded as safe, (GRAS) chemicals can inhibit the growth of various food-borne and food-spoilage microorganisms [11]. However, due to the complexity of the food matrix, which includes the presence of intrinsic and extrinsic elements that interfere with compound bioactivity, the acquired in vitro results cannot be extended to food.

Therefore, ginger, *Zingiber officinale* is normally used in many countries as spice and condiment to give a strong taste that stings the tongue in foods although, indigenous to South-East Asia [12]. Rhizomes of ginger has long been used as a traditional herb world-wide particularly in Ayurveda, America, China, and Europe, and also a valuable remedy to aid digestion of food. India is regarded as the top best ginger producer and consumer followed by China, Nepal, Indonesia, Nigeria and Thailand. Ginger has been used in production of soft drinks, baking, meat processing, and cooking [13]. The aroma and flavour in ginger is a consequence of the presence of hydrocarbon compounds (sesquiterpenes and monoterpenoids), while the strong taste in it is because of gingerols, shogaols, paradols and zingerones.

Mostly in the production process of tiger nut milk heat has not been employed, making it difficult to control microbial contamination. The high cost of energy for the refrigerated storage of beverages such as tiger nut milk, has necessitated the need to find alternative methods of extending the shelf-life of the product through the use of natural preservatives such as clove and ginger. In addition to these, consumers are becoming more skeptical about the use of chemicals due to toxicity in their beverages.

Since there are many negative effects on beverages preserved by freezing, pasteurization, irradiation or addition of chemicals as observed in many literatures, the result of this work will help to determine whether natural preservatives (i.e clove and ginger) will do better in extending the shelf life of the product. However, the use of dates as substitute to sugar will make the milk suitable to diabetic patients. This study was aimed at determining the bacteriological and mycological quality of milk produced from tiger nut. Furthermore, the study assessed the effects of clove, ginger and a combination of the two (2) on the storage stability of the product.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Collection

All the raw materials used in this study were from plant origin; tiger nut (*Cyperus esculentus*), from semi-dried tubers, clove (*Syzygium aromaticum*), from dried buds of flowers, ginger (*Zingiber officinale*), from dried rhizomes and dates (*Phoenix dactylifera*), from fruits of plants. These samples were purchased from Maiduguri Monday market and transported in polythene bags to Microbiology Laboratory, Faculty of life Science, University of Maiduguri, Borno State for further analysis.

Tiger Nut Milk Production

The tiger nuts (Figure 1) were manually sorted from dirt, washed using clean water, and one kilogram (1kg) of it was soaked in three liters (3L) of clean water for twelve hours (12h), three kilograms (3kg) of the deseeded dates (Figure 2) were milled into slurry. About two liters (2L) of water was added into the slurry making the ratio 1:5:3 (w/v/w) and sieved through a muslin cloth to obtain a homogenized filtrate called tiger nut milk (Figure 3) as described by [14]. Temperature and pH of the sample were recorded from the production time up to spoilage time. Proximate analysis of the milk, dates, tiger nut, clove and ginger was carried out in National Agency for Food and Drugs Administration and Control (NAFDAC). About one hundred centiliter (100cL) of the milk was used as control (treatment A), one hundred centiliter (100cL) contained three grams (3g) of clove (Figure 5, treatment B (v/w), one hundred centiliter (100cL) contained three grams (3g) of ginger (Figure 6), treatment C (v/w), and another one hundred centiliter (100cL) contained three grams (3g) of both the clove and ginger, treatment D, (v/w), (Figure 4). Two (2) other replicates were made with same quantity of the milk, a hundred centiliter (100cl) but blended with different amount of the preservatives, five and seven grams (5 and 7g) respectively. The samples were stored at ambient temperature in the laboratory; evaluate its microbial content every day while spoilage was observed every morning, day and evening, by determining a change in any of the organoleptic parameters by the respondents.

Figure 1. Tiger nut

Figure 2. Deseeded dates

Figure 3. Tiger nut milk (T.M.D)

Figure 4. A treatment and a replicate of Tiger nut milk

Figure 5. Clove powder

Figure 6. Clove powder

About twenty-eight (28g) of Nutrient agar powder was weighed and dissolved with 1000mL of distilled water. The mixture was then heated to dissolve the powder completely and sterilized by autoclaving it at 121°C for 15 minutes. It was allowed to cool to about 45°C and dispensed as desired into Petri-plates to solidify.

MacConkey agar

Forty-seven grams (47.0g) of MacConkey agar powder was weighed using weighing balance, and transferred into a conical flask containing 1000mL of distilled water; it was sterilized by autoclaving at 121°C for 15 minutes, allowed to cool at 45 – 50°C, and then poured into sterile petri plates.

Malt Extract Agar

Fifty grams (50g) of Malt extract agar was weighed, suspended into 1000mL of distilled water, add chloramphenicol capsule (250mg) and heated to boiling point with frequent agitation. The medium was sterilized by autoclaving at 115°C for 10 min, allowed to cool to about 50°C and dispensed into petri plates.

Microbial Evaluation of the Sample

One milliliter (1mL) of the tiger nut milk was serially diluted and inoculated using spread plate method on Nutrient and MacConkey agar for bacterial and malt extract agar for fungal growth. The microbial load was determined. Colonial characteristics, gram staining and biochemical tests were used to identify the bacterial isolates present in the sample. Fungal identification was carried out macroscopically using morphological characteristics of the fungi such as colour, texture, topography, etc. and microscopically. Bacterial and fungal isolates were sub-cultured on the relevant media in order to have a pure culture for further characterization.

Identification of the Bacterial Isolates

Morphological identification through Gram staining and relevant biochemical characterizations that include the catalase test, urease production test, methyl red reaction test, Voges–Proskauer test, indole production test, citrate test, oxidase test, H₂S production test, triple sugar iron test were carried out [15].

Gram Staining

The pure bacterial culture was gram stained as follows;

The colony was picked, smeared on a glass slide and heat fixed. The primary stain (crystal violet) was added onto the slide and allowed to stay for one minute. The crystal violet dyes the cell wall of the bacteria species present, which was then rinsed with water. Grams iodine (mordant) was poured on to the slide and allowed to stay for one minute and rinsed again with water. Decolorizer (ethanol) was added and allowed to stay for 30 seconds which removed the primary stain from gram negative bacteria present. It was also rinsed with water. Finally, counter stain (safranin) was applied and allowed to stay for one minute to stain those cells (gram negative) that have lost the primary stain as a result of decolorizer. It was also rinsed with water.

Microscopy

The glass slides containing the smear were examined microscopically with x100 objective lens under oil immersion for the observation of gram reaction and morphological characteristics of the bacterial cells. Gram positive bacteria appeared purple in colour while gram negative cells appeared pink in colour. After gram staining and microscopy, the isolates were sub-cultured into universal bottle containing nutrient agar in a slant form for subsequent use in biochemical test [16].

Biochemical Tests

Catalase Test

A drop of 3% (v/v) H₂O₂ (hydrogen peroxide) was placed on a slide. Using an inoculation loop, a small amount of inoculum from the growth medium was then added onto the glass slide. Presence of catalase was observed by the formation of gas bubbles [17].

Urease Test

Slant of urea medium in universal bottle was inoculated with a loop full of the isolates. The bottles were then incubated for 24 hours at 37°C. Change in coloration from yellowish orange to pinkish indicated urease positive [16].

Voges-Proskauer Test

In Voges-Proskauer test methyl red was added first to the two-day old culture and 0.6 mL of 5% naphthol solution added and shaken. The test tubes were sloped and examined after 15 minutes. A red colour indicated a positive Voges-Proskauer reaction [16].

Indole Production Test

Loop full of the isolates was inoculated in a sterile nutrient broth. The incubation was done at 37°C for 48 hours. After incubation, 0.5 mL of Kovac's reagent was added and shaken. It was examined after one minute. A red ring coloration in the reagent layer indicates indole production (i.e indole positive) while a yellow or no coloration indicated indole negative [17].

H₂S Production Test

A test tube of nutrient broth with the test organism was used. The lead acetate paper strip was inserted in the neck of the tubes of the medium. It was incubated at 35-37°C and examined daily for blackening of the lower part of the strip.

Citrate Utilization Test

On a sterile Simon's citrate medium, a loop full of 24 hours old culture was inoculated aseptically. It was then incubated at 37°C for 24 hours after which it was examined daily for turbidity for a period of 3 days [17].

Triple Sugar Iron (T.S.I)

Triple Sugar Iron (T.S.I) Inoculum from sub-cultured plates was picked with a sterile straight wire loop and stabbed on the butt and then streak on the surface of slant. The inoculated test tubes then incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Since TSI is a composite media, several reactions were read from it after the 24 hours of incubation. Gas production was determined by the presence of bubbles or cracks on the agar or complete disruption of medium, Hydrogen sulphide production was determined by the blackening of the whole butt or a streak or ring of blackening at the slant butt junction, Motility was determined by the presence of growth along the area that was stabbed by the straight wire loop. Yellowing of the butt indicated glucose fermentation, formation of a pink/red colour at the slant indicated the presence of lactose and sucrose fermentation [17].

Identification of the Fungal Isolates

A drop of 70% ethanol was added onto a clean microscopic glass slide, before the addition of fungal specimen using a sterile mounter, teased and ensuring the sample mixes well with the alcohol. Using a pipette, a drop or two of Lacto-phenol Cotton Blue Solution was added before the ethanol dries off. The stain was carefully covered with a clean sterile coverslip avoiding air bubbles and examined microscopically at 40X, to observe for fungal spores and other fungal structures as described by [18].

Evaluation of Organoleptic Property of the Sample

A structured close ended questionnaire containing (9) cardinal points (like extremely, like very much, like moderately, like slightly, neither like or dislike, dislike slightly, dislike moderately, dislike very much and dislike extremely) based on acceptance rate was used by panelists or respondents to assess the Organoleptic parameters of the milk which includes; appearance or colour, aroma or flavour, mouth feel, sweetness, taste and palatability of the samples using the method of [19].

Determination of Storage Stability

The ten (10) samples (with and without preservatives) stored at room temperature in the Laboratory were observed for spoilage, and cultured daily for microbial assessment of the samples as adopted by [19].

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive Statistics (percentage and mean) of observations was used in this study.

RESULTS

Microbial Quality Assessment of the Tiger Nut Milk

The Table (Table 1) contains (3) treatments, each with different preservatives (clove, ginger and a combination of both), and each treatment has (3) replicates, each with different concentrations of the preservatives (3, 5 and 7g/L). Treatment B with concentration of 7g of clove had the highest mean pH (4.9), while treatment C with concentration of 7g of ginger had the lowest mean pH (3.5). However, highest bacterial load was observed in treatment B with concentration of 3g of clove (52×10^7 cfu/ml), while treatment D with concentration of 7g of clove and ginger had the lowest (28×10^7 cfu/ml).

There was a decrease in bacterial population every time the pH value decreased, making the product sour (more acidic). The highest pH value was recorded in treatment B, with concentration of 7g of clove (6.3), while the least pH was recorded in treatment C, with concentration of 7g of ginger (2.1) over time. Evident to the bacterial load, treatment C, with concentration of 3g of had the highest number of viable colonies (85×10^7 cfu/ml), while that with the lowest colony counts was treatment B, with concentration of 7g of clove (47×10^7 cfu/ml).

Morphological and Biochemical Characteristics of Bacterial Isolates

Table 2 shows the characterization of the bacterial isolates from clove, ginger, and the tiger nut milk produced, with or without preservatives and at different concentrations. Different preservatives represented the treatments (B, C and D) while different concentrations represented the replicates (1, 2 and 3). Staining properties were meant to identify the bacterial shape and gram reaction, while the biochemical tests were for further identification to species level. According to the information on the test reactions by the isolates, *Bacillus*, *Proteus*, *Micrococcus* and *Staphylococcus* species were gram positive, while *Pseudomonas* was gram negative.

Bacterial load and the isolated microbes in clove, ginger and the produced tiger nut milk

As presented in Table 3 were the viable number of bacterial colonies (38 , 47 and 51×10^7) in clove powder, ginger powder and the produced tiger nut milk respectively. The bacterial isolates include; *Staphylococcus* from clove, *Staphylococcus* and *Bacillus* spp. from ginger, while *Proteus*, *Pseudomonas* *Micrococcus*, *Staphylococcus*, *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, *Alternaria*, and Yeasts spp were identified from the produced milk product.

Table 1: Triplicate mean pH value and total bacterial count in the milk produced with different preservatives, at different concentration and stored under ambient temperature for three (3) days

Treatments	concentration	Mean pH Value	Mean Bacterial load ($\times 10^7$ cfu/ml)
B	(3g)	4.2	52
	(5g)	4.5	42
	(7g)	4.9	32
C	(3g)	3.8	40
	(5g)	3.6	36
	(7g)	3.5	33
D	(3g)	4.5	45
	(5g)	4.2	43
	(7g)	4.1	28

Key:- B= tiger nut milk with clove, C= tiger nut milk with ginger and D= tiger nut milk with clove and ginger.

Table 2: Morphological and Biochemical Characteristics of Bacterial Isolates

Sample	Staining property		Biochemical Tests											Bacterial spp.
			Cat	MR	V.P.	Ind	Cit	Urea	T.S.I.		Glu	Lac	Gas	
	Shape	GR									Suc	Gas	H ₂ S	
Clove	Cocci	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	<i>Staph. spp.</i>
Ginger	Cocci	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	<i>Staph. spp.</i>
	Rod	+	+	-	+	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	<i>Bacillus spp.</i>
T.M.D	Rod	+	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	<i>Bacillus spp.</i>
	Rod	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	<i>Proteus spp.</i>
	Rod	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	<i>Pseudomonas spp.</i>
	Cocci	+	+	-	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	<i>Micrococcus spp.</i>
B1	Cocci	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	<i>Staph. spp.</i>
	Rod	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	<i>Pseudomonas spp.</i>
C1	Rod	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	<i>Bacillus spp.</i>
	Cocci	+	+	-	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	<i>Micrococcus spp.</i>
D1	Cocci	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	<i>Staph. spp.</i>
B2	Rod	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	<i>Pseudomonas spp.</i>
C2	Rod	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	<i>Bacillus spp.</i>
D2	Cocci	+	+	-	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	<i>Micrococcus spp.</i>
B3	Rod	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	<i>Proteus spp.</i>
C3	Cocci	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	<i>Staph. spp.</i>
D3	Cocci	+	+	-	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	<i>Micrococcus spp.</i>

KEY: G.R- Gram Reaction, Cat.- Catalase, M.R- Methyl Red, V.P- Voges-Proskaur, Ind- Indole, Cit.- Citrate, T.S.I- Triple Sugar Iron, Glu- Glucose, Lac- Lactose, Suc- Sucrose, H₂S- Hydrogen Sulphide, Gas- Gas Production and T.M.D- tiger nut milk drink.

Table 3: Bacterial load and the isolated microbes in clove, ginger and the produced tiger nut milk

Sample	Cfu/g or ml	Microbes
Clove	38 x10 ⁷	<i>Staphylococcus spp.</i>
Ginger	47 x10 ⁷	<i>Staphylococcus</i> and <i>Bacillus spp.</i>
Tiger nut milk (control)	51 x10 ⁷	<i>Proteus, Pseudomonas, Micrococcus, Staphylococcus, Aspergillus, Alternaria, Penicillium</i> and <i>Yeasts spp.</i>

Key :- cfu- colony forming unit,

DISCUSSION

Many food drinks are naturally prone to spoilage and as such require an aseptic method of preparation, storage and distribution in order to stay safe for a longer time. Food contamination is not only microbial and the sources also may differ [19]. In this context, the bacterial count in the preservatives were 38x10⁷ (cfu/g) in clove and 47 x10⁷ (cfu/g) in ginger, with about 62 x10⁷ in the stock solution of the milk produced. Result of this study shows an appreciable bacterial load when compared to the report by [20] who recorded about 1.33x10⁴, 2.03x10⁵ and 7.60x10¹cfu/ml in tiger nut milk stored at room temperature.

The result by [21] was observed to contain a load of 1.71-4.68x10³cfu/ml (mean standard error), of triple determinations under ambient temperature which is higher than the result of this work. High bacterial count than the presented in this study was reported by [22], with a total viable count of 6.3-8.5x10⁵cfu/ml. The tiger nut

milk produced in this study was confirmed "safe" for human consumption as there was a strong correlation between the international standard organization value (5.00×10^3 cfu/ml) of bacteria and less than 1.00×10^7 cfu/ml in relation to 0.62×10^7 cfu/ml by this study. The clove powder used in the study was found to be contaminated with *Staphylococcus* species and the ginger with *Staphylococcus* and *Bacillus* spp., whereas, the produced milk with *Micrococcus*, *Proteus* and *Pseudomonas* spp.

The source of these organisms can be related to human, environment, materials and or the samples used. This result is in agreement with those by [20] and [23] who reported the presence of *Staphylococcus* and *Micrococcus* spp. among the contaminants in tiger nut milk. Added bacterial contaminants in this work were *Proteus* and *Pseudomonas* spp. which makes it different from the report by [20] and also did not correspond with the record by [23].

A similar work by [19] confirmed the presence *Staphylococcus* and *Pseudomonas* spp. in tiger nut milk. [24] certified that the quality, safety and shelf life of foods depends on the microbial population and diversity which in turn reduces spoilage and the cause of infection. *Aspergillus niger*, *A. flavus* and Yeasts spp. yielded by this research work correspond to the findings by [20] who reported same fungal isolates in tiger nut milk. In similar work by [15], tiger nut milk was populated with *Saccharomyces* spp. as recorded by this work. In line with this finding, are the reports by [4] and [25], that *Aspergillus* spp. is among the most dominant fungi in tiger nut milk. Other fungal species observed in this work were *Alternaria alternata* and *Penicillium brasilianum*.

CONCLUSION

Aseptic techniques in local production of tiger nut milk reduce microbial contamination. Tiger nut milk was successfully prepared from tiger nut tubers and sweetened with dates. Clove, ginger and a combination of the two (2) proved effective on the storage stability of the tiger nut milk produced by extending its shelf-life to more than (48) hours at ambient temperature.

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